

Matrices, Special Relativity and Zitterbewegung in Photons

Francesco R. Ruggeri April 23, 2018 N.B.

In a series of notes [2] - [9], we saw that a 2x2 matrix model was naturally contained in Einstein's 1905 energy momentum equation $E^2 = m^2 + p^2$ (1). In particular, p/E was written as $\cos(a)$ which in turn was written as $\cos(a/2)^2 - \sin(a/2)^2$. This expression was then written in matrix form:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \cos(a/2) & \sin(a/2) \\ \sin(a/2) & -\cos(a/2) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \cos(a/2) \\ \sin(a/2) \end{pmatrix}$$

A similar process was applied to m/E . It was then argued that the various matrices represented operators with their expectation values representing parameters. For example:

$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$ was taken to be the velocity matrix with an expectation taken using $(\cos(a/2), \sin(a/2))$ yielding v .

An energy matrix was constructed and time dependence of operators written as $\exp(iHt)$ $V \exp(-iHt)$. This in turn led to Zitterbewegung results [1].

The purpose of this note is a little different. We wish to start with matrices, with no assumption of relativity, and see if special relativity arises. In particular, we wish to apply the theory to the photon. We will obtain a matrix equation related to Pythagoras' theorem for right angle triangles and will then try to apply it to light.

2x2 Matrices

For two dimensional space, a common basis is $(1,0)$ and $(0,1)$. These are eigenvectors of the identity matrix as well as the matrix

$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$ (which we saw above). Now, $(0, 1)$ can be written as $\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$.

Let us call the first matrix V and the second M to give them names.

M takes an eigenvector of V and transforms it into the second eigenvector. Equivalently, it rotates an eigenvector by 90 degrees, as the two eigenvectors are orthogonal.

The eigenvectors of V are $(1,0)$ and $M(1,0)$. If one takes a sum of these and operates with M , one immediately sees that $(1,0)+M(1,0)$ is an eigenvector of M , namely $(1,1)$. Operating on $(1,1)$ with V yields $(1,-1)$ which is the other eigenvector. (A factor of $1/\sqrt{2}$ yields orthogonality.)

Thus, $(1,1)$ and $V(1,1)$ are eigenvectors of M or: $(1,0)+M(1,0)$ and $V(1,0) + VM(1,0)$.

Combining 2x2 Matrices

Let us now construct the following matrix:

$aV + bM$ (2) with a and b being two arbitrary constants. Let us further define a vector:

$x|+M\rangle + y|-M\rangle$ where $|+M\rangle = (1,1)/\sqrt{2}$ and $|-M\rangle = (1,-1)/\sqrt{2}$

Let us find values which make this an eigenvalue equation, namely:

$(ax-by)|-M\rangle + (ay+bx)|+M\rangle = Q(x|+M\rangle + y|-M\rangle)$ where Q is the eigenvalue.

This leads to $a^2 = Q^2 - b^2$ or Pythagoras' theorem for a right angle triangle.

Expressing variables in terms of the expectation value of V

Let us denote the expectation value of V with $x|+M\rangle + y|-M\rangle$ as v .

Let $x^2 + y^2 = 1$. Then:

$x|+M\rangle + y|-M\rangle = x(1,1)/\sqrt{2} + y(1,-1)/\sqrt{2} = (x+y, x-y)/\sqrt{2}$ so

$$v = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} (x+y) & (x-y) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} (x+y) \\ -(x-y) \end{pmatrix} \text{ or } xy = 2v$$

Now $(x+y)^2 = 1+v$ and $(x-y)^2 = 1-v$ thus

Thus: $x+y = \sqrt{1+v}$ and $x-y = \sqrt{1-v}$

Consider operating on equation (2) with $\langle +M|$. This yields: $ya+bx=Qx$ Next, operate with $\langle -M|$ to obtain $ax-yb=Qy$.

This gives: $a/Q=v$ and $b/Q=\sqrt{1-v^2}$

Scenario for Light

Let us consider a photon bouncing back and forth in the y direction. It will have a frequency related to E and a momentum such that $E=pc$. (We set $c=1$.) Let the length of the y axis, denoted L , be such that it fits one wavelength. Next, consider placing the photon in a box moving with velocity v in the x direction. To the observer in the lab, the photon will move in a straight line making an angle a with the x axis. It will still bounce back and forth, but the motion will look like an isosceles triangle. Thus, if the velocity of the photon remains c , then because the length traversed is greater namely $L/\sin(a)$, the frequency must also be greater, namely

$E_{\text{new}} = E_{\text{old}} \frac{2L}{\sin(a)}$ Similarly, $p_{\text{new}} = p_{\text{old}} \frac{2L}{\sin(a)}$.

Now, $v = \cos(a)$ where $c=1$. Thus, $\sin(a)=\sqrt{1-v^2}$.

These results appear in the two matrix combination (2) that we have created in above sections. Thus, one may argue that the two matrix combination represents a photon which obeys special relativity.

Interpretation of the 2x2 Matrix Combination

Equation (2), the combination of the two matrices, produces the special relativistic results for a photon. (It also produces Einstein's energy momentum equation (1).) One may argue, however, that no matrices are needed to produce special relativity. In such a case, the two matrix approach would simply be a mathematical exercise. We argue here, however, that the matrices and eigenvectors can have physical relevance and may even lead to some potentially new assumptions.

Let us consider the eigenvector of M, namely (1,1). In the two matrix combination (2), we transform to the eigenvector $(\sqrt{1+v}, \sqrt{1-v})/\sqrt{2}$. We immediately, see a lack of symmetry which is needed to ensure that the expectation value of V is v. It is not simply the case that the energy of the photon in the moving frame (speed v in the x direction) is different from that in the rest frame, the angle of travel is different. The lack of symmetry already suggests that a different kind of acceleration is occurring. In the case of the photon in the lab frame, it bounces back and forth in the y direction. Acceleration affects its entire momentum. Such is not the case in the moving frame and the vector $(\sqrt{1+v}, \sqrt{1-v})$ demonstrates this. This is the vector representing the new frequency (as seen from the lab) and it contains this different kind of acceleration. The M and V matrices simply take projections yielding $\sqrt{1-v^2}$ and v. Thus, one is obtaining a little more information about a photon than displayed in the wave equation which follows from Maxwell's equation. That equation is only related to $E_{\text{new}}=E_{\text{old}}/\sqrt{1-v^2}$

Zitterbewegung of a Photon

Equation (2) can be applied to light and also to a relativistic particle. In the particle case, the combined matrix $aV+bM$ represents an energy matrix and $\exp(-iHt)$ appears to behave as a time evolution operator. Thus $O(t) = \exp(iHt) O \exp(-iHt)$ where O is an operator. This yields zitterbewegung equations for operators such as V and dV/dt . One may suggest applying this same technique to a photon. Normally, there is no energy matrix for the photon, but we have suggested in a note [6] that $E^2 + B^2$ expression for electromagnetic energy can also be solved using the 2x2 matrix approach. This would suggest that a photon should also have zitterbewegung. In addition, Einstein's energy momentum equation (1), when divided by m^2

where m is the rest mass, applies to the photon. It is just the Pythagoras' equation applied to a triangle with c as the hypotenuse, v/c on the adjacent and $\sqrt{1-(v/c)^2}$ on the opposite. No doubt this has been pointed out many times in the literature.

This is interesting, however, because we are examining a photon without considering its electric E and magnetic B fields. The matrices together with $\exp(-iHt)$ may be able to yield information about a photon's behaviour. (Here $H=aV+bM$. It is not really a Hamiltonian in the photon case, but it acts as a time evolution operator when applied to vectors.)

In previous notes [2]-[9], expressions have been given for zitterbewegung for $X(t)$, $V(t)$ and $dV(t)/dt$. It was found that there seems to be periodic motion over the surface of a sphere. Thus, there is a disturbance in space which may be physically associated with a wavelength. In the case that we can apply the 2x2 matrix model to E^2+B^2 , zitterbewegung may be associated with the E and B fields of a photon.

Let N be the energy density of a photon. Then: $1 = E^2/N + B^2/N$. It should be possible to define a matrix similar to V (the velocity matrix) and call it B/\sqrt{N} . In addition, one can define a matrix related to E/\sqrt{N} . These should be: $\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}$ and $\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$ respectively.

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \quad \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Solutions for these already exist in [2]-[9], [namely:

$$B/\sqrt{N} = V + i \cdot 5 \sin(2\sqrt{N}t) dV/dt + \sin^2(\sqrt{N}t)(\cos(a) H/\sqrt{N} - V)$$

$$\text{where } V = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and } H/\sqrt{N} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(a) & \sin(a) \\ \sin(a) & -\cos(a) \end{bmatrix}$$

a is the angle between the direction of the movement of light and the x axis and $E = \sqrt{N}$

$$\begin{aligned} &E/\sqrt{N} \\ &= \exp(iHt) \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \exp(iHt) = \\ &\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + i \cos(\sqrt{N}t)\sin(\sqrt{N}t) 2p \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + 2\sin^2(\sqrt{N}t)2\cos(a)\{\sin(a)V - \cos(a)\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}\} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

Here, V is the velocity matrix $\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}$ and $\begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$ is related to dV/dt . $E = \sqrt{N}$ and t is time.

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$H = aV + bM.$$

Thus, there may be zitterbewegung for the E and B fields as well as for V (velocity) for a photon. The V zitterbewegung would be the same as B/\sqrt{N} .

It should be noted that a charged particle, such as an electron also has an expression for energy density given by $1 = E^2/N + B^2/N$ and that similar arguments from the 2x2 matrix approach may apply to it. It seems that this warrants further investigation as the calculations for

zitterbewegung [1] are based on the evolution operator $\exp(-iHt)$. It was argued in notes [2]-[9], that the "energy" matrix appearing in the 2x2 matrix model behaves as an evolution operator in that it transforms vectors into its own positive energy eigenvector. It is on this basis that we attempt to apply zitterbewegung calculations to the square root electromagnetic energy density matrix.

For the photon, there is also really no Hamiltonian here, but we apply zitterbewegung calculations to the V matrix which appears in (2) i.e. the matrix formalism which is equivalent to both Einstein's energy momentum equation (1) and a photon triangle with sides c , v and $\sqrt{1-v^2}$.

Conclusion

It appears that one can start with a purely mathematical treatment of 2x2 matrices and obtain equations for light and relativistic particles. In previous notes [2]-[9], Einstein's 1905 energy momentum equation (1) was taken as a starting point and so it appeared that the ideas emerging applied only to relativistic particles. The energy momentum equation, however, is simply Pythagoras' equation for a right angle triangle and this can be applied to light as well, demonstrating the close relationship between light and relativistic particles. These equations also seem to lead to zitterbewegung for both the photon and relativistic particle. This is important, because zitterbewegung may possibly give a physical basis for the wavelength for both relativistic particles and light. Furthermore, energy density for electric and magnetic fields is given by $E^2 + B^2$ for both photons and charged particles. If one could apply the 2x2 matrix approach to this expression, then one could obtain zitterbewegung associated with the E and B fields as well.

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